

TASKS AND TYPES OF LABOR EDUCATION, ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE COMPREHENSIVE DEVELOPMENT OF A CHILD'S PERSONALITY

Ergashev Ikhtiyor

Associate professor of the department of specialty sciences,
Andijan faculty of Tashkent Institute of Finance,
Andijan, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10418658>

Abstract: The significance of the work lies in the fact that the main provisions and conclusions set out in the work can be used for a deep and comprehensive study of the labor education of children, as well as directly for practical and creative tasks.

Key words: labor education, teacher-researchers, development, social relations, social institutions, personal status, structure of society.

Many teachers of the past and present point out that children show interest in work and a desire to work already in early age. They are drawn to the affairs of their elders and copy their actions. This is the origin of hard work.

Today, teacher-researchers are faced with serious and responsible tasks of developing and experimentally testing the content of work for children of different ages, developing means, methods and forms of organizing work, studying the mechanism of influence of work on the development of a child. It is these questions that science has always dealt with, and today it has provided answers to many of them. [3, p.17]

According to its content, the work of preschool children is divided into four types: self-service, household work, work in nature, manual and artistic work.

Self-care is the work of a child aimed at serving himself (dressing and undressing, eating, sanitary and hygienic procedures). The quality and awareness of actions varies from child to child, so the task of developing self-service skills is relevant at all age stages of preschool childhood.

In younger groups, the teacher shows how to perform actions: how to hold tights, a dress, so that they are comfortable to put on. The demonstration should be step-by-step, with an explanation. You can't just tell your child: "Here are the tights, take them like this and put them on." Everything is difficult for a baby: to take it, to stretch the elastic band, and to insert the legs into not one stocking, but two. At first, the adult helps at every stage, and over time gradually reduces the share of his help, support, and hints.

When teaching self-service work, the teacher uses looking at pictures. They are useful in forming ideas about the sequence of actions. It is advisable to use special manuals to help teach children how to fasten buttons and lace shoes. You should show your child the correct techniques, introduce him to the “little secrets” that make it easier to perform certain actions (it is better to fasten the buttons on a shirt from the bottom, not from the top, then you can control what you are doing, see the last button and the last loop and connect them). [3, p.18]

The content of self-care work changes at different age stages and as children master work skills. If a child has mastered the ability to dress independently, he needs to be taught to do it neatly, beautifully, quickly, and to take care of his appearance and hairstyle. Children are taught the habit of taking care of things, not getting dirty, not tearing clothes, and folding them carefully.

The content of self-care work for older preschoolers also includes self-care: preparing the workplace before starting drawing; cleaning and even washing (at home) cups, spoons after meals, making the bed, tidying up toys and books.

Having learned self-service, a child acquires a certain independence from an adult and develops a sense of self-confidence. Of course, even in older preschool age, children sometimes need the help of an adult, but still, before entering school, they should already be able to do a lot on their own.

Household work. This is the second type of work that a child of preschool age is able to master. The content of this type of labor is cleaning the premises, washing dishes, doing laundry, etc. If self-service labor is initially intended for life support, for taking care of oneself, then household labor has a social orientation. The child learns to create and maintain his environment in an appropriate manner. A child can use his household skills both in self-care and in work for the common benefit.

Children of middle and senior preschool age are capable of more varied household work and need less help from an adult. Gradually, children acquire independence in this type of work. The teacher uses methods of showing, explaining, discussing the work process and results, evaluating, teaching certain methods of performing labor operations (how to wring out a rag so that water does not flow down the sleeves, etc.). [6, p.179]

It is important to form in preschoolers an idea of the importance of household work for everyone and for everyone personally. It is this work that makes it possible to show the child that he himself can make the environment in

which he lives beautiful and pleasant. The teacher always draws the children's attention to this side.

Modern household work is made easier by technology. It is also useful to teach children to use household machines. At home, a child can vacuum the carpet on the floor and watch the washing machine in action. You just need to be sure to familiarize children with safety rules and try not to leave them alone with equipment. But under the supervision of an adult and together with him, a child can, using equipment, engage in household work.

Practice shows that by older preschool age, some children lose interest in this type of work. The reason is that the child has already mastered the necessary skills. Children do everything that is required of them: wash toys, make beds, etc., but they do it without interest. The content of household work can be complicated by expanding the range of responsibilities or introducing a new object for the use of already developed skills (wiping dust not only in the toy closet, as has always been the case, but also on the windowsill, on furniture in the bedroom).

Labor in nature is distinguished as a special type of labor. The content of such work is caring for plants and animals, growing vegetables in the garden, landscaping the area, participating in cleaning the aquarium, etc. Labor in nature has a beneficial effect not only on the development of labor skills, but also on the education of moral feelings, laying the foundations of environmental education. [6, p.180]

In younger groups, children's attention is drawn to plants and animals. The teacher organizes observations of animals and at the same time tries to maintain the interest of the kids. Together with an adult and under his guidance, the child cares for living objects.

The responsibilities of children of senior preschool age are much broader. And this is understandable. The child already knows more, knows more.

Labor in nature has its own characteristics. Thus, work in nature contributes not only to labor education, but also to moral, aesthetic, mental, and physical development.

Manual and artistic labor, by its purpose, is labor aimed at satisfying the aesthetic needs of a person. Its content includes the production of crafts from natural materials, paper, cardboard, fabric, wood. This work contributes to the development of imagination and creative abilities; develops small arm muscles, promotes endurance, perseverance, and the ability to finish what you start. Artistic work in a preschool institution is presented in two directions: children

make crafts and learn to decorate the group room for the holidays with their products, design exhibitions, etc. [6, p.181]

In relation to preschool age, we can also talk about the emergence of mental work. Any work is characterized by an effort aimed at achieving a result. The result, as we said above, can be materialized (an object made by a child, a grown plant), can be presented through an improvement in quality (washed doll clothes, a cleaned bird cage), or can act as a logical solution to some problem. The latter is the result of mental labor. The teacher teaches children to “think before they act,” to explain to themselves and others the course of their thoughts, to draw conclusions and conclusions, and, finally, to receive satisfaction from the solution they independently found. A child’s mental work has all the structural components of work activity: motive, goal, process, result.

The study of issues of labor education at the stage of preschool childhood is a pressing problem. We also worked on this topic. An analysis of theoretical literature shows that psychologists and educators have turned their attention to this problem and are considering different directions for solving it.

In the course of our research, the hypothesis was confirmed. Indeed, in older preschool age it is possible and advisable to carry out the process of labor education of children. Success is determined by taking into account the characteristics of the labor education of children, if we remember that children’s labor is conditional, is used mainly for educational purposes, that it is unproductive, therefore the quality requirements are different than at other levels of education; if labor education is considered in the context of the moral education of preschool children; if you take into account their interests when working with children; if, when working with preschoolers, we focus on their work interests.

At the same time, the organization of the pedagogical process based on the joint activities of children and adults is essential in solving the problems of labor education.

In this study, we determined and experimentally tested the effectiveness of forms and methods for the labor education of preschool children. They also constitute those features of the implementation of labor education of children that the teacher takes into account.

Labor education is one of the important tasks at the present stage of preschool education. The kindergarten, the first link in the children's education system, plays an organizing and directing role.

Labor education plays an important role in the comprehensive development of a child's personality and in preparing the child for school. Children develop moral guidelines and an awareness of the usefulness of work.

References:

1. Abdullayev Tursunboy Yakhshiboyevich. The concept and types of public control and the relationship between society and the state. International scientific journal "Interpretation and researches" Volume 1 issue 9, p 4.
2. Bure R. Organization of children's work and management methods // Preschool education. - 2013. - No. 4
3. Vitkovsky A. Instilling hard work in preschoolers // First of September. - 2010. - No. 2
4. Education of a preschooler at work // Ed. Nechaeva V.G. - M; 1983
5. History of preschool pedagogy in Russia: Reader: Textbook. manual for pedagogical students. institutes / Comp. N.B. Mchedlidze et al. Ed. S.F. Egorova. - 2nd ed., revised. and additional - M.: Education, 1987. - 432 p.
6. Litvinovich O.V. Joint labor activity in kindergarten // Preschool pedagogy.- 2010.-No. 4.- P.28-31.
7. Makarenko A.S. Pedagogical poem. Ped soch., T.1." - M., 1978.
8. Methodological recommendations for the program of education and training in kindergarten / Ed. M.A. Vasilyeva.-M.: Education of a preschooler, 2008.

